

CROSS-LINGUISTIC COMPATIBILITY OF LANGUAGE AND SPEECH UNITS REPRESENTING THE CONCEPT OF COURAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219963>

ANNOTATION

This article describes the study of the term concept, its linguistic and cultural features and forms. The principles of the linguistic and cultural research of the concept and the methods of determining the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the concept are discussed, as well as the opinions expressed by famous linguists about them.

Key words: Linguistics, concept, modern associations, cognitive concept, nominative density, paradigm of conceptualism, category apparatus, self-awareness, phraseological combinations, modified components, individual words, Monoequivalent, polyequivalence.

It is known that language and discourse units that make up the linguistic landscape of the concept of "courage" in Uzbek and English, in particular, their communicative-pragmatic, national-cultural aspects, and the issues of their recreation in a foreign language have not been studied as the object of special monographic studies.

Today, along with the study of language as a means of communication and knowledge, the tendency to view language as a set of cultural codes in the reflection and representation of the linguistic landscape in the human mind is growing. Phraseology in this sense is a relatively more cultural information-carrying layer of the lexicon, which shows the cultural experience of different ethnic groups, their unique way of seeing and perceiving the world. From this point of view, the phraseological fund of the language is a source of valuable information about the culture and mentality of the people. People's history, traditions, values, morals and manners will be included in them. In the words of V. A. Telia, "the phraseological structure of the language is a mirror, in which the linguistic-cultural community identifies with its national self-awareness." Understanding the term phraseological unit in a broad sense, by this term we mean idioms, phraseological combinations, proverbs and proverbs.

The creator of such national phraseologisms is the people, in which the hopes, thoughts, truths and spirituality of that people are reflected. According to Professor M.E. Umarmho'jaev, "phraseological units are word combinations containing at least two completely or partially semantically modified components, individual words cannot become phraseological units no matter

how much they are processed." A.E. Mamatov defines phraseological units as follows: "any stable lexical-semantic units recorded in dictionaries, which are structurally equivalent to a phrase or a sentence, have figurative, generalized meaning, lexical elements have a partial or complete figurative meaning, are included in the circle of phraseological units".

The famous Russian scientist V. V. Vinogradov divides phraseological units into three groups according to their semantic properties. Phraseological units belonging to the first group are called phraseological phrases. Phraseological units in this language are figurative, and their overall meaning does not derive from the meaning of the components. (drop a melon, bite the wax, dogs in blanket, have other joli to try). Phraseological units belonging to the next group are such stable combinations that, although they have a unified figurative meaning, their general meaning comes from the meaning of the components: to stand out, to have a black heart, to fly to the wind.

Phraseological combinations belonging to the third group are such combinations that have a partially figurative meaning, the components of which are replaced or can be replaced by homonyms: add fuel to the fire (flame).

Analyzes of English and Uzbek explanatory dictionaries, phraseological dictionaries, translations of works of English and Uzbek writers showed that phraseological units in the compared languages have monoequivalent or polyequivalence characteristics.

By monoequivalent phraseological units, we mean group combinations that have only one equivalent in the translated language: have the courage of one's convictions Keep lip one's courage= not to be discouraged, as brave as a lion .

Monoequivalents can be divided into fully or partially equivalent stable units. Fully monoequivalent phraseological units are phraseological units that have the same meaning, lexical structure, expressiveness and grammatical structure: A stout heart=fearless heart; have heart to do or to say with=the bride of the sea=bride of the sea (Venice refers to the rule of the seas), the asses bridge=joke, donkey bridge (the fifth theorem in the book of Euclid's geometry, for students to understand named for its difficulty).

Partially equivalent phraseological units are monoequivalents that have the same meaning, but differ in terms of lexical structure and grammatical structure, and they can be divided into three categories: a) Uzbek English phraseological units that differ in terms of lexical structure, but have the same meaning and semantic aspects, and are close in expressiveness. equivalents: it

was found that some phraseological units belonging to this group can also be translated by the antonymic translation method. In such cases, the negative meaning expressed implicitly is expressed in Uzbek and Russian languages through negative constructions: shut one's heart to fear=not knowing fear; steel one's heart against fear=try not to show fear.

b) In the Uzbek equivalents of the English phraseological units belonging to the second group, there is no similarity in terms of expressiveness and stylistic function, but there are different aspects in the word structure: pluck up heart(spirit) = courage, sweat, use all courage.

c) the Uzbek equivalents of the third group of English phraseological units are similar in meaning and stylistic aspects, but differ from each other in terms of expressiveness. It should be noted that the grammatical structure of such categories of phraseological units may or may not be appropriate. It was observed that most of the phraseological units with expressiveness in the language are partially translated by equivalent phraseological units: take one's courage in both hands = take one's courage in both hands

The fact that proverbs belonging to this group can be translated through antonym equivalents is evident in the following examples: none but the brave deserve the fair (proverb)

Polyequivalent phraseological units are units that have more than one equivalent in the Uzbek language, and when translating them from one language to another, the practicing translator has to choose the variant that fits the given context. For example: the phraseological unit A man of his hands has equivalents in Russian such as храбрый, mujestvennyy chelovek, opotnyy chelovek, master na vsyo ruki, zolotye ruki, and in Uzbek, such equivalents as brave, brave, manly man.

Phraseological units that do not have an equivalent in Uzbek were also identified in the materials of the compared languages. We tried to find a similar alternative (analogue) of this category of phraseological units, and it consisted of the following. Knight without Fear and without reproach = fearless and without resentment (etymology is French chevalier sans peur et sans reproche: the nickname of the French knight Basrda).

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